

DLV Implementation - Consent Under Control with ProPrivacy: Business Process Compliance Verification for GDPR-Consent Requirements

Marco Robol
University of Trento
Via Sommarive 9, 38123 Povo, Trento, Italy
`marco.robol@unitn.it`

Mattia Salnitri
University of Bergamo
Via Salvecchio 19, Bergamo, Italy
`mattia.salnitri@unibg.it`

Elda Paja
IT University of Copenhagen
Rued Langaardsvej 7, Copenhagen, Denmark
`elpa@itu.dk`

This document presents the DLV (Answer Set Programming) implementation of the ProPrivacy framework for verifying GDPR consent requirements in business processes. The implementation provides a formal, executable specification of the verification rules discussed in the main paper, allowing for automated compliance checking of Business Process Model and Notation 2.0 (BPMN 2.0) business process models. The code is organized into two main parts: the representation of business processes and consent authorizations, and the verification rules for GDPR requirements including data minimization, freely given consent, and specific consent. A custom requirements framework is also provided to allow domain experts to define additional constraints specific to their organizational context.

1 DLV code for business processes

This section presents the DLV implementation of the formal framework for representing and analyzing business processes. DLV is a Answer Set Programming (ASP) system that provides a declarative language for knowledge representation and reasoning. The implementation defines predicates and rules to capture the structure of BPMN 2.0 business processes, including participants, activities, data objects, events, and their relationships. We first show how business processes are represented in DLV, then how authorizations of consent are modeled, and finally how inference rules are used to compute walks through the process.

1.1 DLV representation of a BPMN 2.0 Business Process

In the DLV implementation of the formal framework, business processes are described using predicates `participant`, `activity`, `dataObject`, `event` for atomic elements, `controlFlow` for sequence flow associations, `writeDO` and `readDO` for data associations, and `executed` for executor associations.

Figure 1 shows an excerpt from the case study. In this small sub-process, the family doctor visits a patient and generate a referral before dismissing the patient.

Listing 1: Example of representation of a business process in DLV

```
1 participant (FamilyDoctor).  
2 activity (GenerateReferral).  
3 dataObject (Referral).
```


Figure 1: Excerpt of a BPMN 2.0 diagram from the case study

```

4 event (AppointmentStart) .
5 flow (AppointmentStart , VisitThePatient) .
6 flow (VisitThePatient , GenerateReferral) .
7 writeDO (GenerateReferral , Referral) .
8 executed (VisitThePatient , FamilyDoctor) .

```

Listing 1 shows a sub-part of the DLV code that represent the process in Figure 1. Facts in lines from 1 to 5 declare the elements of the process, lines 6 and 7 represent the sequence flow associations from *AppointmentStart* to *VisitThePatient* activities and from *VisitThePatient* to *GenerateReferral* activities, line 8 represents the data association from *GenerateReferral* activity to *Referral* data object, and line 9 represents the executor association from activity *VisitThePatient* to participant *FamilyDoctor*.

1.2 DLV representation of authorizations of consent

This subsection describes how consent and its authorizations are represented in DLV. Consent authorizations define which privacy operations (collection, processing, dissemination) are permitted on specific data objects during the execution of activities. In DLV, the predicate `consent` is used to declare a consent, while predicate `auth` is used to declare an authorization part of a consent, where attributes represent respectively the consent element, the data object, the activity, and the authorized privacy operation.

Listing 2: Example of privacy policies in DLV

```

1 consent (docC) .
2 auth (docC , referral , uploadRef , dissemination) .
3 consent (apssC) .
4 auth (apssC , referral , medicalExam , collection) .
5 auth (apssC , results , uploadRes , processing) .

```

Listing 2 shows the DLV code for the authorizations of the two consents from Tables ?? and ?. For example, authorization `auth (docC , referral , uploadRef , dissemination)` from line 2, expresses that the family doctor consent *docC* authorizes the dissemination of the *referral* data object in the execution of the activity *uploadRef*.

1.3 DLV inference rules for business process walks

This subsection presents the DLV inference rules used to compute walks through a business process. A walk represents a possible execution path from a start event to other elements of the process, following control flow associations. The ability to compute walks is fundamental for verifying GDPR requirements, as it allows us to determine whether certain activities can be reached and under which conditions. In DLV, walks of a business process are inferred starting

from a start event and following control flow associations. The predicate `walk` is used to represent the existence of a walk between two elements of the process.

Listing 3: DLV walk inference rules based on a two-attributes predicate

```
1 walk(X,X) :- start(X).
2 walk(X,K) :- walk(X,Y), flow(Y,K).
```

Listing 3 shows DLV rules used to infer business process walks. Line 1 initializes a new walk by start navigating a business process from a start event. Line 2 creates an extended versions of existing walks by following control flows.

For example, given the process of Figure 1, `walk(AppointmentStart, GenerateReferral)` represents the existence of a walk from the event *AppointmentStart* to the activity *GenerateReferral*.

Another use of the predicate `walk` is in the case of three parameters, where the additional parameter is an element that is included in the walk.

Listing 4: DLV walk inference rules based on a three-attributes predicate

```
1 walk(X,X,X) :- start(X).
2 walk(X,Y,K), walk(X,Z,K) :- walk(X,Y,Z), flow(Z,K).
```

Listing 4 shows DLV rules used to infer business process walks that goes through some specific element. Similarly to rules in Listing 3, line 1 initializes a new walk, while line 2 creates an extended versions of existing walks.

For example, given the process of Figure 1, `walk(AppointmentStart, VisitThePatient, GenerateReferral)` represents the existence of a walk from the event *AppointmentStart* to the activity *GenerateReferral*, through the element *VisitThePatient*.

2 DLV code for GDPR requirements

This section presents the DLV implementation of the verification rules for GDPR consent requirements. Each requirement is translated into a set of DLV rules that detect violations of the requirement. The rules leverage the business process representation and walk computation capabilities described in the previous section to verify properties such as data minimization, freely given consent, and specific consent. We also present the ProPrivacy custom requirements framework, which allows domain experts to define additional constraints specific to their context.

2.1 DLV implementation of the minimization requirement

Listing 5: DLV implementation of minimization property

```
1 excessiveAuth(A) :- auth(C,M,A,collection), activity(A1), not messageFlow(A1,
  A,M).
2 excessiveAuth(A) :- auth(C,M,A,dissemination), activity(A1), not messageFlow(
  A,A1,M).
3 excessiveAuth(A) :- dataObject(DO), auth(_,DO,A,processing), not readDO(A,DO)
  , not writeDO(A,DO).
4 excessiveAuth(A) :- message(M), auth(C,M,A,processing), activity(A1), not
  messageFlow(A1,A,M).
```

Listing 5 shows the DLV implementation for the verification of the data minimization property. **Line 1** implements minimization of collection. An excessive authorization exception is thrown in the case that collection is authorized but no message is received. **Line 2** implements minimization of dissemination. An excessive authorization exception is thrown in the case that dissemination is authorized but no message is sent. **Line 3 and 4** implement minimization of processing. In the case of a data object, an excessive authorization exception is thrown in the case that processing is authorized but no data object is read or produced. In the case of

a message flow, an excessive authorization exception is thrown in the case that processing is authorized but no message is sent.

2.2 DLV implementation of the freely given consent requirement

Listing 6: DLV rules to verify the existence of some process execution trace that does not require any authorization

```

1 -free(A) :- element(A), auth(_,_,A,_).
2 free(A) :- element(A), not -free(A).
3 freeExec(FROM, FROM) :- start(FROM), free(FROM).
4 freeExec(FROM, TO) :- freeExec(FROM, X), flow(X, TO), free(TO),
                        not -freeExec(FROM, TO).
5 -freeExec(FROM, TO) :- start(FROM), not freeExec(FROM, X), flow(X, TO),
                        parallelJoin(TO).
6 freeExec(FROM) :- start(FROM), end(TO), freeExec(FROM, TO).
7 freelyGivenException :- start(FROM), not freeExec(FROM).

```

Listing 6 shows the DLV implementation for the verification of the freely-given consent property. **Lines 1 and 2** infer elements that does not require any consent, identified with the predicate `free`, and those who does require some consent, `-free`. **Line 3** initialize BPMN 2.0 execution rules considering only elements free from any consent. **Line 4** propagate execution on following elements **Line 5** implements BPMN 2.0 execution rules in the case of join elements. **Line 6** terminates the execution of the process when an and event is reached. **Line 7** require a free process execution for each start event.

2.3 DLV implementation of the specific consent requirement

Listing 7: DLV implementation to verify the specific consent property

```

1 nonConsentSpecific(A) :- auth(C,_,A,_), auth(C2,_,A,_), C2!=C.
2 freeOrConsentSpecific(C,A) :- auth(C,_,A,_), not nonConsentSpecific(A).
3 freeOrConsentSpecific(C,A) :- consent(C), free(A).
4 forward(X,C) :- start(X), freeOrConsentSpecific(C,X).
5 forward(Y,C) :- forward(X,C), flow(X,Y), freeOrConsentSpecific(C,Y), not -
                        forward(Y,C).
6 -forward(Y,C) :- freeOrConsentSpecific(C,X), flow(X,Y), not forward(X,C),
                        parallelJoin(Y).
7 backward(X,C) :- forward(X,C), end(E).
8 backward(X,C) :- backward(Y,C), flow(X,Y), forward(X,C).
9 specific(X) :- forward(X,C), backward(X,C).
10 specificityException(A) :- auth(_,_,A,_), not specific(A).

```

Listing 7 reports DLV rules used to verify the existence of a consent-specific process-execution-trace for each activity. **Lines 1, 2, and 3** infer activities that either do not require any consent or that require only one consent. Following lines apply BPMN 2.0 execution rules to explore the process by considering only one consent at a time. **Line 4** initializes execution from start node. **Line 5** propagates execution to the following nodes. **Line 6** implements join gateways. **Line 7** finalizes the execution when an end node is reached. **Line 8** propagates the finalized execution on previous nodes. **Lines 9 and 10** throw a `specificityException` for activities that do not satisfy the specific consent property, meaning that are not part of any free or consent-specific execution trace.

2.4 DLV implementation of the ProPrivacy custom requirements framework

Listing 8: Disjunctive rules implementing BPMN 2.0 execution rules

```

1 step(1,X) v -step(1,X) :- start(X).           % Step 1
2 :- step(1,X), step(1,Y), X!=Y.             % At most one start
3 started :- step(1,X). :- not started.      % At least one start
4 ended :- end(X), step(N,X). :- not ended.  % At least one end
5 step(M,Y) :- step(N,X), #succ(N,M), flow(X,Y), not alternativeFork(X), not
   parallelJoin(X).                          % All if no alternatives
6 step(M,Y) v -step(M,Y) :- step(N,X), #succ(N,M), flow(X,Y), alternativeFork(X
   ).    % Alternatives
7 step(X) :- flow(X,Y), step(N,Y).
8 :- flow(X,Y), not step(X).                 % At least one alternative
9 :- exclusiveGateway(G), flow(G,X), flow(G,Y), step(N,X), step(N,Y), X!=Y.
   % At most one in case of exclusive
10 -joined(G) :- parallelJoin(G), flow(X,G), not step(N,X).
11 step(M,G) :- parallelJoin(G), not -joined(G), flow(X,G), step(N,X), #succ(N,M
   ).    % Join all in case of parallel

```

Listing 8 shows DLV rules used to generate process execution traces, which are based on BPMN 2.0 execution rules. Here a description:

- Create a trace for each start event in which this is executed as the first step.
DLV rules: (line 1) For each start event, create two traces, one in which it is executed as the first step, the other one in which it is not executed; (line 2) Allow at most one start to be executed at step 1; (line 3) Require at least one start to be executed at step 1.
- Continue until an end event is executed.
DLV rule: (line 4) Require at least an end event to be executed at some step.
- In the case of an element followed by a single control flow or in the case of a parallel gateway, execute all the next elements.
DLV rule: (line 5) In a new step execute all the activities that follow an element executed at current step, that are not alternative fork gateways or parallel join gateways.
- In the case of alternative gateways duplicate the execution trace for each exiting control flow or a combination of those.
DLV rules: (line 6) In the case of alternative gateways two execution traces are created for each exiting control flow; (lines 7 and 8) Require at least one control flow to be taken; (line 9) Allow at most one control flow to be taken in the case of exclusive alternative gateways.
- In the case of a parallel join gateway, execute next element only in the case that all previous elements are executed at some previous step.
DLV rules: lines 10 and 11.

Listing 9: Example of custom constraint that requires the existence of a process execution trace that includes the activity `a1`

```
:- not step(a1).
```

Listing 9 shows an example of a custom requirements to force the execution of a specific activity. The implementation consists of a DLV constraint that invalidate all traces that does not include the execution of the the activity `a1`.

3 Availability of the DLV implementation

The complete DLV implementation of the ProPrivacy framework, including the verification rules presented in this document, is available as open-source software on GitHub at:

<https://github.com/marcorobol/ProPrivacy-DlvScalability>

The repository contains:

- The DLV engine files (`pro_privacy_engine.dll` and `pro_privacy_engine4.dll`) with all verification rules for GDPR requirements
- Java source code for executing DLV and generating test inputs
- Scalability evaluation data and results demonstrating linear scaling performance up to 400+ activities
- Comprehensive documentation with BPMN2 to ASP translation rules and usage examples

The implementation has been evaluated for scalability using systematic tests with three synthetic patterns (parallel branching, sequential depth, and nested gateways), showing execution times below 150ms even for processes with 400+ activities, making it suitable for offline design-time verification of business process compliance.

References